

CHAPTER -ONE

INTRODUCTION

Now we live in information-based society. Library is the storehouse of all information. An institution is complete if this institution use a sound and effective information and communication technology. A library is a main factor to the literate society and impact a central position in higher education. The tradition of libraries concept in Bangladesh is not new. The truth is that, a quality education cannot be run without use ICT in a library. However, the university library should be the center of all activities of a university. The center of all activities of a university. The university of Rajshahi Library started in 1953. It is the ancient and biggest library in Bangladesh. This library is biggest library in South Asia. Library is a treasure house of rare books, manuscripts and period ideals. It also attempts to stock the latest books and periodicals published in Bengali and in English. Most of the university libraries in the country are still providing traditional type of services to their users. But the pleasure fact is that, Rajshahi University Central Library provides automation based library activities and ensures the latest library services to the users.

We are very hopeful that if the authority and the Government be aware, it is possible to highlights that the Rajshahi University Central Library is the model of a modern and up-to date library.

Statement of the problem

In the age of information explosion, libraries and information resource centers have become multimedia centers due to adoption of new technological devices and changing nature of their information storage, retrieval and services. During the last 25 years, the computers and telecommunication technologies began to build up an

information society, which has crossed the geographical limitations and has provided facilities to access into global information systems. As a result, nature of modern librarianship has changed considerably with the advent of new technologies.

Digital library, virtual library, library automation are very common terms in present world. Bangladesh is not far behind regarding these applications. Countries leading academic and special libraries are running now fully or partially automation system. For issuing books, journals, CD-ROMs and other reading materials check out and check in have been introduced. Automatic prescribed request form, SMS library service through cell phone, telephonic library service and response to any queries are no more dreams now.

Though library automation has become an old topic in developed countries, it is still a new and emerging issue in our society. A few libraries have started using computers in their institutions. But the present condition of library automation in Bangladesh is still in its infancy. Many people related to this field do not have a clear concept about the term 'Library Automation'.

Automation is the technology concerned with the design and development of process and system that minimize the necessity of human intervention in operation. Knowledge is growing rapidly; libraries are procuring the large amount of various collections like books, periodicals, e-resources & non-book materials to fulfill the needs of the library users.

Library automation is to prepare a database for library collections to proper organizing, retrieving the information & providing the information to the users within the time.

Objectives of the study

Every research work has some vital objectives. This study reviews the extent of automation application in Rajshahi University Central Library. The main objectives are

- To find out the present situation of automation system as well as overall trends of Rajshahi University Central Library
- To explore the problems hindering library automation faced by the library authority.
- To recommend some solutions of the problems faced by the library. Besides some solutions are given for adoption of new computer technologies as well as to improve the automation system of the library.

Importance of the Study

Through research activities it is possible to collect various data on specific fields. For this reason it is very essential to acquire practical knowledge of research besides theoretical knowledge. The study bears the following importance

- It will be helpful to know the overall condition of Rajshahi University Central Library
- It will also be helpful to know the automation system of Rajshahi University Central Library
- It will be helpful to improve the automation system of libraries as well as students for their study.

Scope & Limitations of the study

The title of this research work is “Current trends of library automation in Bangladesh: A case study on Rajshahi University Central Library . This work is limited into only one university library.

As the researcher is a new one-research fellow of research field, the study has certain mistakes and limitations, like-lack of time, money, prior and experience.

Methodology

The research method is followed for this research case study. Basically the researcher use structured questionnaire including both open and close ended questions to collect information from the Rajshahi University Central Library. Personal interview with library professionals and field visits to library were undertaken for the collection of information . The researcher also use some primary and secondary sources like books, journals, research articles, etc.

Literature Review

A literature review is a text written by someone to consider the critical points of current knowledge including substantive findings, as well as theoretical and methodological contributions to a particular topic. According to Bruce-“The review forms an important chapter in a thesis where its purpose is to provide the background to and justification for the research undertaken.” It is the most crucial part for conducting any research. It is secondary source and as such do not report any new or original experimental work. According to Cooper-“A literature review uses as its database reports of primary or original scholarship and does not report new primary scholarship itself.” A literature review can be interpreted as a review of an abstract accomplishment. Its main goals are to situate the current study within the body of literature and to provide context for the particular reader.

Haravu (2004) wrote a book entitled ‘Library Automation: Design, Principles and Practice’. In which he explained the history and development of library automation systems as a background to an extensive analysis of each single methodology behind establishment library automation. He not only illustrated the automation of acquisition, cataloguing, circulation control and serials in depth, but also dedicated a chapter each on file and data structure and how to optimize critical single aspects of these individual key systems.

Riaz (1992) made a focus on “Library Automation” where he explained as the computer facilities began to proliferate and became cost effective, the library administrators started thinking in term of utilizing computers to help process unprecedented flood of literature. He also identified the use of computers with different technologies in different areas of library and information centers.

Rao (1996) brought out a book entitled “Library Automation” where he said information technology in general and computer technology in particular has been the indication of library and information systems and services. They have helped in speeding up and precision of information collection, processing and distribution. Also the development of microcomputers coupled with telecommunication technology has helped compressed and portable development of information systems.

CHAPTER TWO

LIBRARY

Concept of Library

Library is a social institution charged with the function of proper using and disseminating human culture civilization. It is one of the important media for mass

communication and an agency which plays an effective role in the society, so that a bright, brave and prosperous world would come into being. Once upon a time library was regarded as a store house and books were meant for preservation, the librarian was supposed to be a custodian, who did not encourage the use of books. The readers were expected to use the library on their own. At the most if a reader asked for a book then so called librarian would pass on the book and leave him alone. As far as possible a librarian kept out of the way of the readers libraries tended to be passive and archival institutions. Perhaps, there was not enough incentive for them to become of name. Now a day's library with a new conception is regarded as a science institution. However, the name library comes from the Latin word librarian which in turn comes from liber meaning a book in the literal or general sense a library is a room or a building where a collection of books periodicals manuscripts and other materials are kept for use but not for sale or show. Its main aim is to enable the users to make the most effective use of the resources and services of libraries. Definition: Some important definition has been given below: -

According to the Oxford English Dictionary Library is – “A building, room or set of rooms containing a collection of books for the use of the public or some portion of it, or the members of a society—a public institution or establishment charged with the care of a collection of books”.

According to Encyclopedia of Information and Library Science:

- “The term used for a collection of books and other literary material which have been other literary material which have been kept for reading, study and consolation”.
- “The term is used for a place building, room or rooms set a part for the keeping and use of a collection of books etc”.

According to ALA Glossary of Library terms- has defined library as 1.

- “A collection of books and similar material organized and administered for reading consultation and study”.
- “A room, a group of rooms or a building in which a collection of books and similar material, is organized and administered for reading, consultation and study”.
- "Synonymous with series as part of the collective title for a group of books issued in the same form by a publication". *

According to UNESCO

“Any arranged collection of printed Any organized collection of printed books and periodicals or any other graphic or audio-visual materials with a staff to provide and required to meet the informational research, educational or recreational needs of users”.

According to Pears Butler “the library is a social organization a necessary unit in the social fabric, effectively planned and organized for transmitting the accumulated experience of society through the instrumentality of books and other graphic and pictorial materials maps, charts photo-records, micro-films etc”.

According to C.R Butler

“Library is 'A collection of books assembled for use as against collection assembled for sale for display for the purposes for which books may be assembled.” “From the above definition it is to say that, library means, irrespective of the title, any organization collection of printed books and periodicals or of any other graphic or audio visual materials, and the service of staff to provide and the use of such materials as are required to meet the international reaches, educational or recreational needs of its users”.

Types of Libraries

- National Library
- Public Library

- Special Library
- Academic Library

Functions

As library is regarded as a social institution, it performs following functions:-

- Life-long education.
- Information documents on all subjects including local, national and international affairs to serve economic, political and social welfare.
- Proper use of leisure
- Advancement of culture
- Preservation of library heritage for posterity.

Academic Library is based on the following categories--

- School Library
- College library
- University Library.

Academic Library

Concept of Academic Library

Academic Library is an educational institution. That is what their libraries are established for serving students, teachers, research fellows are usually known as academic library. Academic library must be related with school, college university etc.

Definition: Because of clear discussion some important definition about academic library has been given below.

According to Harrods librarians Glossary "Those of universities, Polytechnics, colleges, Schools and all other institutions forming part of or associated with educational institutions.

According to ALA Glossary of Library terms: “A library forming an integrated part of a college organized and administered to meet the needs of its students and faculty’.

So, it is to say that, these library which is related with higher educational institutions is recognized as ‘Academic library Objectives of Academic Library: Academic library bears students, teachers or researchers to build up themselves.

Apart from these, the main objectives of academic library are as follows:

- To fulfil the requirements of various students involves in different sections by providing academic information demands.
- To serve the researchers by providing research articles.
- To assist, in the development to overall social, economical, political situation.
- To help the users directly by giving academic degree required information. So academic library is called the backbone of all educated users.

Types of Academic library

Academic library are of the following types:

- School library
- College library
- University library.

Functions of Academic Library

Academic library has to perform the following functions:

- To establish a principle for developing the library.
- If required academic library collects audio-visual materials with books for students and teachers,
- To establish principle for book acquisition.

- Classification and cataloguing is another important function of academic library for arranging books.

A brief discussion about these has been given below

School Library School library is the place from where a person acquires food for mental growth and development.

According to Dr. S.R. Ranganathan: “The school library has been variously described in the literature as an information center, a learning center, a learning laboratory, a media center, a research center. The school library has two main principal components. Such as: One is concerned with the information personnel, equipment and space needed to complement and support the other one. And the other component is concerned with the planned activities and services that assist the students. However, school library becomes a force for educational excellence.

College Library: In general, a college is regarded as an institution of higher learning which usually offers a three years or a four years course after school leading to a bachelor's degree. A college library is expected to support the objectives of the college. The basic function of a college library is to assist its programmes.

Definition

According to ALA Glossary of library Terms: “A library forming an integral part of a college organized and administered to meet the needs of its students & faculty”. According to Harrod's Librarians' Glossary “A library established, maintained and administered by a college to meet the needs of its students and faculty. However, college library, in a word, must adequately serve the needs requirements of the teachers and students towards reading study and research.

University Library

Concept of University Library: A university library is a part of a university. It is the part and parcel of university. In other words, university library is an integral part of an institution of higher education. The university library may be a central library that serves all students. It must provide valuable collection for them on all subjects in the curriculum.

Definition

Some important and acceptable defined has been given below:

According to Harrod's Librarians' Glossary

“A library established, maintained and administered by a university to meet the needs of its students and faculty”.

According to ALA: “A library or a system of libraries established, or a system of libraries established and maintained by a university to meet the needs of its students and faculty”.

According to Encyclopaedia Britannica, “University libraries form a group very similar throughout the world. They are descendants of the most ancient libraries. They cover a wide range of subjects in great detail to support the university” own teachers and research workers, but many of them have a status not unlike that of a national library, attracting scholars from all over the world and benefiting from magnificent donations some like the Bolding library (Oxford) and Cambridge university library also receive deposits under the copy rights laws. Some like royal university libraries are also national libraries. Aims of University Library: As university library is an higher educational institution, it has some objectives

The aim of the library can be defined with the framework of the university mission and a library development program can be under take accordingly.

- To meet the educational of all students of the university. 2. To helps to lead every the students of every stage of their life.
- To helps to build up students by supplying various Knowledge.
- To collect, storage and dissemination of information.
- To helps to create better relationship between students and teachers.
- To helps the researcher by giving various research articles or other Literature.
- To helps to synthesis the research project.

Functions of University Library

The university library has to perform the following functions:

- It provides higher education to the students.
- It helps the researcher for their research activities.
- Another important function of university library is to create the manpower.
- It provides sufficient documents or information to the users.
- It creates reading habit to compile a library budget.
- Last but not least is to the reluctant students compile a library budget.

CHAPTER THREE

LIBRARY AUTUMATION

Definitions of Library Automation

The word “automation” has been derived from Greek word “automose”. It means which as power of spontaneous motion or self-movement. The term “automation” was first introduced by D.S. Harder in 1936. Various definitions of automation:

According to Wikipedia, Automation or automatic control is the use of various control systems for operating equipment such as machinery, processes in factories, boilers and heat treating ovens, switching in telephone networks, steering and

stabilization of ships, aircraft and other applications with minimal or reduced human intervention.

According to Merriam-Webster online dictionary, automatically controlled operation of an apparatus, process, or system by mechanical or electronic devices that take the place of human labor.

According to Encyclopedia of Library and Information Science, “automation is the technology concerned with the design and development of process and system that minimize the necessity of human intervention in operation”.

Knowledge is growing rapidly; libraries are procuring the large amount of various collections like books, periodicals, e-resources & non-book materials to fulfill the needs of the library users.

Objectives

Implementing library automation to prepare a database for library collections to proper organizing, retrieving the information & providing the information to the users within the time.

- To maintain bibliographic records of all the materials in a computerized form.
- To provide online catalogue to the users to access from their desk.
- To reduce the duplication of housekeeping operations.
- To prepare various types of reports / statistic within a short time.
- To maintain the circulation section effectively.
- To provide the speed, quality services to the users.

- To maintain various types of materials (books, non-book materials, serials etc.) available in library. • To save the time of the users
- To reduce the duplication of work.
- To provide online catalogue
- To reduce the manpower
- To share the resources through library networking.
- To Increase the operational efficiencies of library staff
- To improve the quality, speed accuracy and effectiveness of services.
- To access other networks on the web.
- To facilitate wider access to information for users.

Essential Requirements for Library Automation

Hardware

Hardware is the primary requirement for library automation; different types of hardware are available in the market. A hardware specification depends on;

- Available budget.
- Size of the data to store.
- Usage load.
- Required speed.
- Features to upgrade when it required.

- Availability of servicing (maintenance).
- Compatible with operating system, what we are going to use.
- Warranty period.

Computer Server

server price may be varying from provider to provider and mainly based on the following:

- Storage capacity
- RAM
- Operating system (Linux, Ubuntu, Windows)
- Supporting software's of library automation software.

Peripherals

a) Keyboard & Mouse

These are the common as minimum needs

b) Printer

Any laser printer to print circulation slips& other library use

c) Scanner

Basic model scanner is required to scan book cover images & library user photographs to upload into the library automation software.

d) Barcode Printer

Barcodes are required as per Code 39.50 standard for books & user library cards.

1. Required barcode printer to generate & to print.

2. Numbers of open source barcode generators are available to generate required barcodes. Some are single barcode generators, some are multiple barcode generators. We can print the barcodes with normal laser printer to reduce the cost of the project.

Open source URL to generate multiple barcodes as Code 39 standard:

<http://openscience.in/koha/index1.html> (Enter the required barcodes in each box)

<http://openscience.in/koha/> (For printing continuous numbers)

We can generate the barcodes from Koha library automation software

Barcode Scanner

- Barcode scanner required for circulation & stock verification.
- Using barcode scanner we can come out from the wrong check outs and check ins.
- It saves the time, manpower & get the exact figures in stock verification by using barcode scanners.

Software

Operating System

Selection of operating system depends on

- Hardware compatibility
- Further supporting from operating system developers
- To be user friendly
- Upgrade facility (service packs)
- Library automation software
- Supporting software's for library automation software.

Software for Library Automation System

Various commercial and open source library automation software is available.
Criteria for Library automation software selection.

- Vision or objectives of library automation.
- Who has developed the software? Whether company, institute or an individual?
- Availability of revisions time period • Available modules
- Capacity to facilitate no of bibliographic records.
- Compatible Z39.50 to retrieve & import data from other databases.
- Compatible with MARC 21 to import or export MARC records.
- Whether the software has the facility to import bibliographic data available in ISO 2709 format and at the same time export data in this format.
- User friendly for customization.
- Facility to customize biblio frame work.
- Menu driven to easy access.
- Whether it can be interfaced with email system.
- No of users using the software.
- Easy upgrade facility with new versions.
- Support from developers
- Availability of customizable OPAC

Cost of the software.

Sl. No.	Core services	Alice	Libsys	New Genlib	Soul	VTLS	Libsuite	Koha
1	Acquisition	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	Cataloguing	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	Circulation	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	Web/OPAC	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	Serials	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	Biblio format	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
7	Data exchange	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
10	Standards	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
11	Community information	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
11	Cost (Approx.)	3.5 Lakh	4.5 Lakh	Open Source	50000	8 Lakh	4.5 Lakh	Open Source

Networking

Networking is required to interconnect the computers, computer peripherals, switches to share the information. The intension of the network is to distribute information among the interconnected users. The network mainly consist of three components i.e. transmission media, mechanism of control and interface unit to the network. Type of network is depends on requirement of the users or objective of the organization to provide the database access to the users. Local Area Network (LAN) is useful to access the library database within the organization.

Wide Area Network (WAN) is required to provide the access facility to outside of the organization.

.Budget

Budget approval to be taken from the management by submitting the library automation project proposal. Allocation of budget will play a key role in library automation project in procuring the hardware, software, library automation software & other computer peripherals. Based on budget availability we will choose the system configuration. i.e. Standalone / IBM server / Cloud server.

Training

Onsite hands-on training is required to library staff members in using each and every module of the library automation software. Training sessions to be conducted in regular intervals & whenever library automation software is updated.

Areas of Automation:

- Acquisition system
- Cataloguing system
- Serials management system
- Circulation
- Members management
- Reports management
- OPAC

Acquisition System

Acquisition is one of the important functions of any library. The goal of the library is to satisfy the users. The users of the library will be satisfied only if the library acquires reading materials based on the user's demands

Acquisition module will be used in two ways i.e.

- a) Normal: it is budget based acquisition by allocating the budget & register suppliers to procure the reading materials.
- b) Simple: Simple bibliographic-data acquisitions

Objectives of an Automated Acquisition System

- To reduce the manual work in acquiring the books.
- Updating ordered list with received books list without any manual mistakes.
- More effective and efficient handling of claims and cancellations.
- More accurate and timely financial data recording, accounting and reporting.
- Improved ability to track orders, receipts, invoice and claims.
- Integration of acquisition with cataloguing and serial control for more effective bibliographic holdings.
- To provide necessary management information reports.
- Improved services to the users through faster, timelier processing of order sand receipts

Cataloguing System

Cataloguing of library materials may do in three ways:

- a) Simple data entry
- b) By converting available items data in to MARC format to import directly to the database.

MARC Edit: Library of Congress developed and providing it freely to download to create marc records or edit marc records.

c) By using Z39.50 to retrieving the required records data from other library databases.

We can download the MARC records from the Library of Congress, WorldCat etc. by using Z39.50. The library catalogue is considered as a mirror of the library because it reflects the collection of the library. The library catalogue is considered as a mirror of the library because it reflects the collection of the library. Automation of cataloguing will reduce the duplication work. Catalogue is made available in a network environment through LAN, WAN. Many users can access the database at same time through OPAC.

OPAC is a catalogue, which is available for searching online. Such OPAC may be searched from a terminal within the library or at a terminal elsewhere in the organization remotely

Telecommunication networks

Today majority of the software's which are used for automation in libraries provide a separate module of OPAC. With the latest developments in integrated systems the OPAC is connected to the circulation system so that the user can come to know whether the document he/she is looking for is currently available in the library or on loan. OPAC also promotes resource sharing program and bibliographic search can be done by author, title, accession number, ISBN, Keywords etc. Search in OPAC is by using Boolean logic or by truncation.

Serials Management System

Serials are published in different intervals with regular or irregularly. Subscriptions maintenance is easy with library automation software.

- To maintain up to date database of received periodicals.
- Easy to know & send reminders to the suppliers for non-receipt of periodicals.
- Renewing the subscribed periodicals before its subscription expiry.
- Routing of periodicals.
- Users can search the OPAC to know the status of current periodicals availability in library.
- Maintaining binding journals details.

Circulation System

The main component of a circulation control system is the transaction of documents i.e. issue and return of documents. This database contains bibliographic details of the documents which provide information on titles, authors and publishing details, which are used in notifying the users about the overdue. Circulation involves the charging and discharging of library materials, reservations, statistics, sending of reminders for the over-due material, etc.

Features of Automated Circulation System

- To know the status of the items.
- Identification of items on loan to a particular borrower.
- Maintaining the reservations& to send available information to users when it returned by the other users.

- Sending circulation alerts i.e. check out & check in.
- Sending system generated reminders to overdue items.
- Printing recall notices for items on long term loan.
- Renewal of loans.
- Notification to library staff of overdue items and printing of overdue notices.
- Calculation of fines.
- Issuing no due certificates

Patron Management

- Easy to maintain users registration with their date of joining and period of membership expiry.
- Providing restrict the borrowing limit to the user groups.
- Predefine the expiry date to a particular user or user groups.
- Provision to provide the login access with user ID & password to know their account from OPAC page.

Reports

We can generate the reports for:

- Accession list.
- Item wise stock list.
- Day wise check out items list
- Day wise check in items list
- Overdue list day wise, or for particular period.
- Not borrowed users list.
- Total borrowers list.
- Most issued items.
- Most borrowed user.
- Not circulated items list.
- Reserved items list.

- Without subject items list.
- Subject wise list.

OPAC

Users can access the OPAC by using local host / system IP within the LAN. If provided public IP, it can be accessible outside the organization. User manual to be provided to the users as soft copy or hard copy. With the OPAC home page, users can do the following things:

- Search the catalogue for new arrivals.
- Search within the selected item type.
- Suggest a book for procurement.
- Reserve an item.
- Know the status of an item.
- Reading history of their account at library.
- Prepare a selected reading list.

Proper training is required to the users to use OPAC effectively

Selection of hardware and software will play a vital role in library automation; it depends on financial assistance from the management. After initiation of open source movement cost of the library automation become nearer. User forums are available to discuss and share their experiences to resolve the problems. There no need an annual maintenance to maintain open source library automation software. Library automation is the only solution to acquire, maintain and discriminate the resources effectively. Proper training, brainstorming secessions are required for library staff members and conducting user education is necessary to use the library automation database effectively.

CHAPTER FOUR

ABOUT RAJSHAHI UNIVERSITY CENTRAL LIBRARY AUTUMATION

Basic information about Rajshahi University Central Library

(Rajshahi University Central Library , <http://library.ru.ac.bd>)

is one of the renowned public university libraries in Bangladesh. According to the present collections, this is the second largest university library in the country. The Central Library is situated at the primordial place of the university. It is a three-storied building superbly designed for preservation, access and use of the library materials. It looks beautiful from outside and provides quiet, calm and comfortable inside environment for the library users. The ground floor of the building is used for storage of reading materials which called the stack section, the nicely designed well-ventilated first floor for general reading area, science & engineering reading area, circulation section, reference section, audio visual section and the second floor for processing section for library materials, periodicals and newspaper section, seminar & conference room, information access center, data center and administrative section.

It is one of the oldest libraries of Bangladesh and, since its inception, has been disseminating information & knowledge to the students, faculty members, researchers and general readers for more than six decades. The library's holdings include a diverse collection of print, non-print, and computer resources for all to use. These books and journals cover all areas of knowledge and information and

reflect the nature of a university with an equal emphasis on humanities, social sciences, business administration, sciences, applied sciences & engineering. The library has some rare books and manuscript collections. It has about three thousand Master of Philosophy (M.Phil.) and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) dissertations. The library has also a huge archive of newspapers and other 'ephemeral' publications.

Recently, the library entered into the automated and digitalized era. The library used world's best open source automated library management system: Koha, DSpace for building and managing institutional repository services. It has also used the best & prominent content management system: Drupal for building & managing the library website. The library established Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) system to ensure the library materials security as well as the better usability of the library resources through self-check in and check out and book drop facilities. Around three thousand user use the library every day.

Total collection of Rajshahi University Central Library:

It has a collection of more than 3, 50,000 printed books, 40,000 journal volumes, and periodicals. It has also 1, 00000+ (subscribed and registered through Research Life) eBooks & more than 40,000 subscribed electronic & online journals.

Types of user:

- Faculties
- Research Scholars
- PG Students
- UG Students
- Administrative Staff
- Supporting Staff

Name of the automation software : koha

Date of implementation of automation package : November 2013

Software:

Rajshahi University Central Library uses world's best open source automated library management system: Koha, DSpace for building and managing institutional repository services. It has also used the best & prominent content management system: Drupal for building & managing the library website. The library recently established Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) system to ensure the library materials security as well as the better usability of the library resources through self-check in and check out and book drop facility

Hardware

Rajshahi University Central Library has a server computer which processor class name zenon and its performance is very good .The server operating system is Linux with debain version. Rajshahi University Central Library has client and web server which processor class is core i5. Rajshahi University Central Library has Power Protection Equipment (UPS) for computers and accessories which is 10 KV and backup devices HDD and mirroring facility .

The library server can be accessed through LAN and WAN.

Peripherals

a) Keyboard & Mouse: Rajshahi University Central Library use keyboard and mouse which are the common as minimum needs

b) Printer

Rajshahi University Central Library has numbers of printer for printing slips and other use

c) Scanner

Rajshahi University Central Library has basic model scanner to scan book cover images & library user's photographs to upload into the library automation software

d) Barcode Printer

Rajshahi University Central Library has barcode printer as per Code 39.50 standard for books & user's library cards.

e) Barcode Scanner

Rajshahi University Central Library has barcode scanner for circulation & stock verification because

using barcode scanner it's possible to come out from the wrong check outs and check in.

It saves the time, manpower & get the exact figures in stock verification.

CHAPTER FIVE

DATA ANALYSIS

Table-1: Automated Sections Rajshahi University Central Library

SI NO	Module	Year
1	Catalog	2013
2	OPAC	2013
3	Circulation	2015
4	Acquisition	N/A
5	Serials Control	N/A
6	Report	2014
7	patron management	2014

Table -1 shows that most of the modules are automated but Only two sections named Acquisition and Serials Control section have not get this opportunity.

Table-2: Acquisition System of Rajshahi University Central Library

SI NO	Features	Yes	No
1	Detailed annual budget		
2	Selection process		no
3	Approval process		no
4	Order process		no
5	Standing order		no
6	Receiving process		No
7	Invoice process		No
8	Payment process		No
9	Reminders to vendor process		No
10	Accessioning process		No
11	Routing and Bindery preparation		No
12	Print of Accession register		No
13	Data conversion in Standard fonnat (ISO 2709)		No
14	Communication through Email to the vendors		No
15	Print of Accession register		No

The analysis of the Table- 2 exhibits that the features in acquisition modules does not use in Rajshahi University Central Library. Rajshahi University Central Library is using koha software that has acquisition module but Rajshahi University Central Library does not use this module for their acquisition. Their acquisition system manually collect resources from the vendors .

Table-3: Circulation Section in Rajshahi University Central Library

SI no	Features	Yes	No
1	Registration of users	yes	
2	Collection of Library Fee	yes	
3	Collection of Library Deposit		No
4	Print of Member Id Card		No
5	Print of Bar Code for Member Id Card		No
6	Calendar for fine calculation and adjusting loan periods for holidays	yes	
7	Renewal of Memberships (continuation)	yes	
8	Issue/Return of items	yes	
9	Issue/Return of Items using Barcode scanner	yes	
10	Renewal of Items	yes	
11	Reservation of items		No
12	Reminders to the users	yes	
13	Issue of No-due certificate	yes	
14	Reporting of Missing of items	yes	
16	Reporting of Lost items	yes	
17	Inter Library Loan (ILL) service for borrowing		No
18	Inter Library Loan (ILL) service for Lending		No
19	Maintenance of withdrawal items	yes	
20	Sending Notices by Email to the users	yes	

Table -3 shows that most of the features of circulation system are present in Rajshahi University Central Library but only four feature named collection of library Deposit, print of member Id card, Print of Bar Code for Member Id Card, reservation of items, Inter Library Loan (ILL) service for Lending, Inter Library

Loan (ILL) service for borrowing are not used in Rajshahi University Central Library

Table-4: Cataloguing section in Rajshahi University Central Library

Library of Congress developed and providing freely to download to create marc records or edit marc records. By using Z39.50 it's possible to retrieving the required records data from other library databases.

Rajshahi University Central Library download the MARC records from the Library of Congress, WorldCat etc. by using Z39.50 and cataloguing code is AACR-2

SI	Statement	YES	NO	Amount
1	Books	Yes		1 lac 20 thousand +
2	Journals	Yes		50 Thousand +
3	News clippings	Yes		
4	Audio-cassette		No	
5	Video-Cassette		No	
6	Reports	YES		

Table -4 present that Rajshahi University Central Library has 1 lac 20 thousand + books, 50 Thousand + Journals which cataloguing code is AACR-2 with MARC 21 format. News clipping and report cataloguing is under processing

Table-5. Usage Study in Serials Control Module in Rajshahi University Central Library

SI NO	Features	Yes	No
1	Detailed annual budget		No
2	Selection process		No
3	Approval process		no
4	Subscription process		no

5	Receiving of Titles process		no
6	New order process		no
7	Renewal Process (continuation of Titles)		no
8	Standing order		no
9	Invoice process		no
10	Payment process		no
11	Check-in process for Title		no
12	Reminder to Publishers/Suppliers		no
13	Print of Accession register		no
14	Print of Invoice register		no
15	Bindery — preparation		no
16	Bindery — order process		no
17	Article Indexing		no
18	Communication through Email to the vendors		no
19	Title History — Change, Split, Merge etc.		no

It is seen from table -5 that all function and features of serial control system are not use in Rajshahi University Central Library

Table-6: Patron Management

SI	Features	yes	NO
1	users registration with their date of joining	yes	
2	period of membership expiry and providing restrict the borrowing limit	yes	

3	predefine the expiry date to a particular user	yes	
4	Provide the login access with user ID & password to know their account from OPAC page.	yes	

Table -6 shows that Rajshahi University Central Library use patron management system by this system easy to maintain users registration with their date of joining and period of membership expiry and providing restrict the borrowing limit to the user groups.

patron management system also predefine the expiry date to a particular user or user groups and provision to provide the login access with user ID & password to know their account from OPAC page.

Table-7: Report management

SI	Features	yes	NO
1	Accession list.	yes	
2	Item wise stock list.	yes	
3	Day wise check out items list		no
4	Overdue list day wise, or for particular period.		no
5	Not borrowed users list.		no
6	Total borrowers list.		no
7	Most issued items.		no
8	Most borrowed user.		no
9	Not circulated items list.		no
10	Reserved items list.		no
11	Without subject items list.		no
12	Subject wise list.	yes	

Table -7 shows that Rajshahi University Central Library use the reports generate through automation system. This system provides only Accession list, Item wise stock list, Subject wise list services

Table-8: OPAC

SI	Features	YES	NO
1	Search the catalogue for new arrivals.	yes	
2	Search within the selected item type.	yes	
3	Reserve an item.	yes	
4	Suggest a book for procurement.	yes	
5	Know the status of an item.	yes	
6	Reading history of their account at library.		no
7	Prepare a selected reading list.		no

Table-8 shows that Rajshahi University Central Library users can access the OPAC .But there is no provision of using o two option namely reading history of their account at library, prepare a selected reading list.

Table -9: Automated services in Rajshahi University Central Library

SI no	Services	yes	no
1	Do you print added subject headings?	yes	
2	Does your library print automated catalog card?	yes	
3	Does your library print shelf list?	yes	
4	Does your library print spine label?	yes	
5	Does your library print Bar Code label for items?	yes	
6	Do you use standard data conversion format (ISO 2709) for data exchange?	yes	
7	Do you use Z39.50 Protocol?	yes	
8	Do you use metadata to catalog electronic resources?	yes	

Table-9 mentions that in the above table services are provided in Rajshahi University Central Library

CHAPTER SIX

FINDINGS

- Rajshahi University Central Library use Catalogue module since 2013, OPAC module since 2013, Circulation module since 2015, Report management since 2014, Patron management since 2014 but Serial Control and Acquisition modules are not using in Rajshahi University Central Library
- Rajshahi University Central Library use koha software that has acquisition module but Rajshahi University Central Library is not using this module for their acquisition. Their acquisition system manually collect resources from the vendors .
- Most of the features of circulation system are provided by Rajshahi University Central Library like

A) Registration of users

B) Collection of Library Fee

C) Calendar for fine calculation and adjusting loan periods for holidays

D) Renewal of Memberships (continuation)

E) Issue/Return of items

F) Issue/Return of Items using Barcode scanner

G) Renewal of Items

H) Reminders to the users

I) Sending Notices by Email to the users

J) Maintenance of withdrawal items

K) Reporting of Lost items

L) Reporting of Missing of items

But following feature are not used in Rajshahi University Central Library

- A) Collection of Library Deposit
- B) Print of Member ID card
- C) Print of Bar Code for Member ID card
- D) Issue of No-due certificate
- E) Inter Library Loan (ILL) service for Lending
- F) Inter Library Loan (ILL) service for borrowing

- Rajshahi University Central Library download the MARC records from the Library of Congress, WorldCat etc. by using Z39.50 and cataloguing code is AACR-2. Rajshahi University Central Library use automated cataloguing system for books, journals, thesis, newsclipping. Audio-cassettes, Video-Cassettes are out of this system.
- All the features of serial control system are not used in Rajshahi University Central Library.
- Rajshahi University Central Library use patron management system this system has following features

A) Users registration with their date of joining and period of membership expiry and providing restrict the borrowing limit to the user groups.

B) Predefine the expiry date to a particular user or user groups and provision to provide the login access with user ID & password to know their account from OPAC page.

- Rajshahi University Central Library use the reports generate system. This system provide only Accession list, Item wise stock list, Subject wise list services. But following functions are not use in Rajshahi University Central Library
- Rajshahi University Central Library users can access most of the options of the OPAC but can not access only two options namely reading history of their account at library, prepare a selected reading list.

CHAPTER SEVEN

PROBLEMS AND SUGGESTIONS

Problems and Suggestions

Bangladesh is one of the few countries of the world which started automation in 1964, but today we are still infancy so far the automation of libraries are concerned. A number of problems contribute to the low degree of computer uses in the libraries in Bangladesh. Though some university libraries have performed a greater role in utilizing IT in libraries yet they are also facing some problems that are affecting the effective communication of information. Now some of these problems are mentioned below:

1. Lack of adequate Skilled Manpower:

The posts of librarians are still vacant in Rajshahi University Central Library. As a result, the library administrator are performing the jobs as chief librarian. Thus it may create hindrance to take a greater initiative in the development of automation process of the library.

2. Lack of Proper Financial Support:

Financial limitation is a great problem that hinders the development of automation in libraries. The Rajshahi University Central Library is handicapped by shortage of funds. As a result measures are not fully taken for financing the automation process. Sometimes it may also create a problem when parent organizations allocate funds for the purchase of computer and related technology, but not its maintenance.

3. Administrative Problems:

Sometimes higher authorities of university are not fully aware of the importance of automation system in libraries. Thus unconsciousness of higher authorities regarding technological development of libraries may seriously causes harm.

4. Lack of proper Technological Facilities:

Another major problem is the lack of proper technological facilities in libraries. DHL has recently developed homemade software package for library but inefficient technical infrastructure often hampered the services. Technological equipment's i.e. computers and other AVM's for providing better services are not sufficient. Moreover, there is also lacks of sufficient technology to convert paper copy into digitized.

In modern automated libraries every book contains computer chip which include valuable bibliographic information about the book itself and the borrower who lend it in different course of time. But in these libraries the book does not contain any computer chip that plays very important role for ensuring proper utilization of particular book.

5. Lack of software packages:

Lack of software packages especially designed to serve Bangladeshi libraries needs. There are readily available packages which do not adapt themselves to the local situation and to the Bangladeshi library environment, or to the libraries particular needs.

6. Lack of Standard Automated Library Model:

Another serious problem is that the automation system of different university libraries appears individualized. Every library performs the works in its own way. In Bangladesh there is no national model or standard for the libraries to participate.

7. Lack of sufficient collection:

Most of the libraries of Bangladesh bear a very few amount of collections.

8. Others problems:

Now some other problems regarding the installation of automation of Rajshahi University Central Library are given below:

- a) In absence of separate suitable and comfortable research branch
- b) Lack of modern electronic and telecommunication media.
- c) Lack of online networking system facilities.
- d) Lack of security system to control loss of books.
- e) Lack of proper bibliographic control of national literature
- f) Insufficient infrastructure facilities
- g) Lack of efficient professional knowledge of staff regarding library automation.
- h) Lack of proper system analysis.
- i) Lack of per-planned decision in the case of automated library systems, j) Lack of proper skill of library staff regarding upcoming new technologies in the field.
- k) Psychological barriers of the library personnel that hinder to accept new technologies for library automation.

Suggestions:

- Skilled manpower should be need to be appointed in the library more for standard library services.
- The University library authorities should allocate sufficient funds to support the purchasing of new technological materials in libraries.
- Higher authorities of university should be aware of the importance of automation libraries.
- More technological equipment's i.e. computers and other Audio-Visual Materials should be added for better-automated library services.
- Libraries with the help of software development firms should develop indigenous software package for the use of computers in libraries in Bangladesh.

- Network flow should be developed.
- Libraries should also develop a centralized database to include all documents & sources of information.
- The library associations of Bangladesh should organize seminars, workshops etc. on computer application facilities to create awareness about computerized library system.
- The library must have a professional librarian with IT background.
- It should be introduced at all level of library activities.
- CD-ROM Service should be developed.
- The mostly used CES/ISTS service should be introduced in DUL.
- A detailed system analysis and design project should be undertaken before implementing fully automated library systems.
- Preparation of automated union catalogue of books and other documents is yet another useful computerized library activity
- A network system among the system among the university libraries should quickly be established. Because networking is one of the most effective ways of serving the user's need comprehensively.
- For increasing their service standard the following attempts should be taken:
 - To implement renew system of books in online.
 - To introduce electronic display board system regarding the arrival of new books in libraries or announces other important notices to students.
 - Provide automatic CAS and SDI service.
 - News clipping service should be automated.
 - Book acquisition procedures are necessary to be fully automated.
 - Automated reference services should be provided.

- E-journal or E-books are provided only authorized students. This discrimination should be avoided. It is necessary to make available all required materials equally accessible to all students of the country.

CHAPTER EIGHT

CONCLUSION AND APPENDINXS

Conclusion:

University library is an integral part of an institution of higher education, University library performs certain activities. In other words, university library is the focal point for those who seek information on diverse subject for those who wish to improve and up-to date their knowledge and education for the purpose of teaching and research. Rajshahi University library has to meet the diverse and growing needs of educational program at the graduate, postgraduates and research level from the beginning stage of the library. For this the university can be called the world of higher education.

This small study provides good indication as to the fact that subscribing computer.

It is a recognized fact that the coming era is going to rely heavily upon information. In order to meet the demand of information, computer must be needed.

However, considering the demand of the age the status of computerization in Rajshahi University Central Library is not satisfactory. It is not possible for us to reach the minimum satisfactory level. Modern information technologies like E-mail, Internet retrieval systems has already been introduced for better library services to the users.

It is of utmost importance that the Rajshahi University Central Library must be improved in overall reading environment. I would like to conclude my study with a view that the library automation is necessary to support the end users and efficient level of services.

It is of utmost importance that the Rajshahi University Central Library must be improved in overall reading environment. I would like to conclude my study with a view that the library automation is necessary to support the end users and efficient level of services.

QUESTIONNAIRE- 1
FOR LIBRARIAN

1. General Information:

- (a) Name of the University : _____
 - (b) Year of Establishment : _____
 - (c) Address : _____

- Phone_____Fax_____
- E-mail_____Website_____

(d) Name of the University Library: _____

(e) Name of the Librarian/Incharge: _____

(f) Year of Establishment : _____

(g) Library Hours : _____

(h) Address : _____

Phone_____Fax_____

E-mail_____Website_____

1. Total Collections (numbers in year

1 wise)

Sr. No.	Items	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
1	Books					
2	Journals (current)					
3	Journals (bound vol.)					
4	Ph.D. Theses					
5	Manuscripts					
6	Rare Books					
7	Audio Cassettes					
8	CD-ROMs/Floppies/Database					
9	Microfilms/Microfiches/Slides					
10	Magnetic Tape/Films					
11	Others (please specify)					

1.2.Total Staff (numbers in year wise)

Sr. No.	Staff	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
1	Librarian					
2	Deputy Librarian					
3	Assistant Librarian					
4	Doc. Officer/Inf. Officer					
5	Sr. Prof. Assistant					
6	Cataloguer					
7	Professional Assistant					
8	Library Assistant					
9	LDC/DEO/Clerk					
10	Library Attendant					
11	Janitor					
12	Book Lifter					
13	Peon					
14	Mender/Binder					
15	Others					

1.3 Total enrolled Users/Members of Library (numbers in year wise)

Sr. No.	Users	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
1	Faculties					
2	Research Scholars					

3	PG Students					
4	UG Students					
5	Admin. Staff					
6	Supporting Staff					
7	Outsiders					

1.4 Annual Budget allocated to the Library (TK. in Lakh in year wise)

Sr. No.	Items					
1	Books					
2	Journals					
3	Non Book Materials					
4	Accessories					
5	Other (please specify)					

1.4 Is there any provision for any separate budget for automation? Yes/No

If yes, please give the % of total budget: _____ (n)

1.5 Library Automation: Are you using any library automation package? Yes/No

If yes, please mention:

1.5.1 Name of the automation package: _____

1.5.2 Date of implementation of automation package: _____

1.5.3 Do you have any server to run the library automation package? Yes/No

If yes, please given the details of Server: _____

1.5.4 Does your Library have adequate hardware for Server and Clients to use the library automation software

a. Server

Poor [] Average [] Very Good [] Excellent []

b. Clients

Poor [] Average [] Very Good [] Excellent []

C . Peripherals (network, etc.)

Poor [] Average [] Very Good [] Excellent []

1.5.5 Please mention Server type by Processor class

486 or below [] Pentium [] corei [] zeone [] Others

1.5.6 Please mention Client type by Processor class

486 or below [] Pentium [] Corei [] zenone [] Others

1.5.7. Does your library have a Web Server?

Yes [] No []

1.5.8 What type of Power Protection Equipment (UPS) does your library have for computers and accessories?

Above 7.5 KV [] 7.5 KV [] 5 KV [] Below3 KV [] Others

1.5.9. Does your library have one or more of the following type of Printers?

Dot Maü•ix [] Inkjet [] Laser [] Line [] Barcode Printer [] Others

1.5.10 Does your library have Barcode Scanner?

Yes [] Yes []

1.5.11. Does your library have Backup Devices?

ZIP [] DAT/Tape [] CD-RWE [] DVD-RW[] HDD[] Mirroring facility] Others []

1.5.12 Does your library server can be accessed through LAN?

Only Central Library [] Some Departments [] All Dependents [] Not accessible [] Others []

1.5.13 Does your library have Electronic Security System for documents?

(at circulation section/library entrance)?

Yes [] No []

1.5.14 Details of the networking

(a) Do you have LAN Facilities? Yes [] No []

(b) Do you have Internet facilities: Yes [] No []

If yes, please tick the Mode of Connectivity:

1. Dial-up Yes [] No []

2. Leased Line Yes [] No []

3. LAN Yes [] No []

If yes, please give the details of LAN:

LAN	Capacity	MB	Bandwidth

2. Automation Section:

2.1 . Which functions have been automated and since how long?

SI NO	Function	Year
	Catalog OPAC Circulation	
	Acquisition Patron management	
	Serials Control Others	

3. Functions and Features in Acquisition Module:

Which of the following indicators do you use for Acquisition module of library automation

Please mention on tick yes or no

SI NO	Statement	Yes	No
1	Detailed annual budget		
2	Selection process		
3	Approval process		
4	Order process		
5	Standing order		
6	Receiving process		

7	Invoice process		
8	Payment process		
9	Reminders to vendor process		
10	Accessioning process		
11	Routing and Bindery preparation		
12	Print of Accession register		
13	Data conversion in Standard format (ISO 2709)		
14	Communication through Email to the vendors		
15	Print of Accession register		

Collection of e-Resources (in numbers):

Sl. No.	acquisition	2012- 13	2013- 14	2014- 15	2015- 16	2016- 17
1	BooksTitles					
2	e-Database					
3	e-Journals					
4	e-Reports					
5	e-Content pages					
6	e-Clippings					
7	e-Books					
8	Others					

3.2 . Mode of communication for acquisition :

Internet via their website

Yes/No

CD-ROM Network	Yes/No
Commercial Online service Vendors	Yes/No
Others (please specify)	Yes/No

3.3 . Criteria for materials for acquisition :

a. Quantity to meet user need	Yes/No
b. Subject relevance	Yes/No
c. Cost effectiveness	Yes/No
d. Authenticity of information	Yes/No
e. After sale maintenance	Yes/No
f. Currency of information	Yes/No
g. Back Issues Facility	Yes/No

Functions and Features Usage Study in Catalog Module

4. 1. Which bibliographic standard does your library use?

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|-----|
| a. Common Communication Format (CCF) | [] |
| b. Machine Readable Catalog (MARC 21) | [] |

4.2. Which bibliographic record are automated ? . '

please mention on tick :

- Books
- ournals
- Bound journal

- News clippings
- Audio- cassette
- Video – Cassette
- Micro -Fiche
- Reports
- Monographs

4.3 . Which cataloguing code do you adopt in your library ?

plz mention on tick

AACR2

B) IFLA

C) LC

D) CLA

7.4 How does the software support bibliographic standard?

Poor [] Average [] Good [] Very Good [] Excellent []

4.5 Does your library use Authority Files?

LCSH Names [] LCSH Subjects [] Series []

Sears List [] Others

5. Functions and Features in Circulation Module

Which of the following indicators do you use to Circulation module of library automation software please mention on tick yes or no

SI no	Statement	Yes	No
1	Registration of users		
2	Collection of Library Fee		
3	Collection of Library Deposit		
4	Print of Member Id Card		

5	Print of Bar Code for Member Id Card		
6	Calendar for fine calculation and adjusting loan periods for holidays		
7	Renewal of Memberships (continuation)		
8	Issue/Return of items		
9	Issue/Return of Items using Barcode scanner		
10	Renewal of Items		
11	Reservation of items		
12	Reminders to the users		
13	Issue of No-due certificate		
14	Reporting of Missing of items		
16	Reporting of Lost items		
17	Inter Library Loan (ILL) service for borrowing		
18	Inter Library Loan (ILL) service for Lending		
19	Maintenance of withdrawal items		
20	Sending Notices by Email to the users		

6. Functions and Features Usage Study in Serials Control Module

Which of the following indicators do you use to Serials Control module of library automation software please mention on tick yes or no

SI NO		Yes	No
1	Detailed annual budget		
2	Selection process		
3	Approval process		
4	Subscription process		
5	Receiving of Titles process		
6	New order process		

7	Renewal Process (continuation of Titles)		
8	Standing order		
9	Invoice process		
10	Payment process		
11	Check-in process for Title		
12	Reminder to Publishers/Suppliers		
13	Print of Accession register		
14	Print of Invoice register		
15	Bindery — preparation		
16	Bindery — order process		
17	Article Indexing		
18	Communication through Email to the vendors		
19	Title History — Change, Split, Merge etc.		

7. Functions and Features Usage Patron Management module

Which of the following indicators do you use to patron management module of library automation software please mention on tick yes or no

SI	Statement	yes	no
1	users registration with their date of joining		
2	period of membership expiry and providing restrict the borrowing limit		
3	predefine the expiry date to a particular user		
4	Provide the login access with user ID & password to know their account from OPAC page.		

8. Functions and Features Usage Report generate

Which of the following indicators do you use to report generate module of library automation software please mention on tick yes or no

SI	Statement	yes	NO
1	Accession list.	yes	
2	Item wise stock list.	yes	
3	Day wise check out items list		no
4	Overdue list day wise, or for particular period.		no
5	Not borrowed users list.		no
6	Total borrowers list.		no
7	Most issued items.		no
8	Most borrowed user.		no
9	Not circulated items list.		no
10	Reserved items list.		no
11	Without subject items list.		no
12	Subject wise list.	yes	

9. Functions and Features Usage OPAC

Which of the following indicators do you use to OPAC module of library automation software please mention on tick yes or no

SI	Statement	YES	NO
1	Search the catalogue for new arrivals.		
2	Search within the selected item type.		
3	Reserve an item.		
4	Suggest a book for procurement.		

5	Know the status of an item.		
6	Reading history of their account at library.		
7	Prepare a selected reading list.		

10 . What Classification scheme does your library use?

DDC [] UDC [] LC [] Others:

10.1 How does the software support classification scheme?

Poor [] Average [] Good [] Very Good [] Excellent []

10.2 Does your library performed following automated system ?

SI no	Statement		
1	Do you print added subject headings?		
2	Does your library print automated catalog card?		
3	Does your library print shelf list?		
4	Does your library print spine label?		
5	Does your library print Bar Code label for items?		
6	Do you use standard data conversion format (ISO 2709) for data exchange?		
7	Do you use Z39.50 Protocol?		
8	Do you use metadata to catalog electronic resources?		

11.0 System Administration, Maintenance and Support Usage Study

11.1 . Is the backup facility inbuilt in the software?

Yes [] no []

11.02 . If backup facility is not inbuilt, how does the library take backup?

Backend database tool [] Full system backup [] Others

11.03.Does the software support to take backup of the following modules?

Acquisition [] Catalog [] Circulation []

Serials Transactions Only whole database

11.04. Which media does your library use to take backup?

ZIP CD-RW DVD-ROM HDD Others

11.05. How frequently do you take backup?

Hourly Daily Weekly Fortnightly Monthly Rarely Others....

11.06. Does the software have report generator to facilitate retrieval of management (inventory) information?

Yes No

11.07. Does your library use statistical reports produced through the software?

Yes no

11.08. Are you satisfied with the system generated reports?

Poor Average Good Very Good Excellent

11.09. Does your library use a single point authorization for all the modules on an individual basis in the software? Yes no

11.10. Does your library use a Module wise (acquisition, catalog etc.) user authentication in the software?

Yes No

11.11. Does your library use software for stock verification?

Yes no

11.12. How much you are satisfied with the technical assistance of a vendor for software upgradation and data migration?

Poor Average Good Very Good Excellent

11.13. How much you are satisfied with the Annual Maintenance Contract (AMC) of a vendor?

Poor [] Average [] Good [] Very Good [] Excellent []

11.14. In what manner does the vendor support on software problems/bugs?

1.E-mail assistance [] 2. Vendor website assistance [] 3. Telephone assistance []

4. On-site visit []

12. Please rate each of the following functions and features of the Library

Automation Software you are now using on the scale of 1-5 where

1 — below average 2—average. 3 — good 4 —very good 5 — excellent

SI no						
1	Acquisition					
2	Cataloguing					
3	Circulation					
4	Serial controls					
5	OPAC with Web interface					
6	Authority control					
7	Routine list management					
8	E-mail notification					
9	Inventor management					
10	Local history files					
11	User authentication					
12	Interfaces to book vendors					

13	Interfaces to serials distributors					
14	Ease of Installation					
15	Reliability (crashes, lost data, etc.)					
16	User authentication					

13. Present situation of automated library system Problem and recommendation

Problem please tick on

LACK OF PROPER PLANNING

LACK OF FUND/ECONOMICAL RESOURCES

LACK OF RESOURCES AND TECHNOLOGY

LACK OF COMPETENT AND WILLING MANPOWER

LACK OF SKILLED OR TRAINED STAFF /PROFESSIONAL

OTHER PROBLEM

Recommendation

Eagerness of the authority

Financial support

Proper planning and design

Support of technology and resources

Skilled and training staff

Others

Suggestions if any:

Name of the Respondent: _____

Designation _____ Signature with Seal

Thank you for your cooperation

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